

Stratifying settlement by building type: assessing the accuracy of the GHS-BUILT-S dataset

Heather R. Chamberlain^{*1}, Gianluca Boo^{†1} and Andrew J. Tatem^{‡1}

¹ WorldPop, School of Geography and Environmental Science, University of Southampton

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Summary

Global high-resolution datasets on buildings and settlement have become increasingly available over the past decade but have lacked attributes on building type or use. The recent release of the GHS-BUILT-S dataset enables stratification of residential and non-residential built settlement globally for the first time. In this study we compare GHS-BUILT-S against national residential household datasets for Germany and Zambia, assessing its accuracy in different built landscapes. Our results show that a greater geographic extent is identified as residential in GHS-BUILT-S, including most mapped residential households in the census datasets. However, areas of non-residential buildings are likely underestimated in GHS-BUILT-S.

KEYWORDS: Settlement data, Residential, Buildings, Census, Satellite Imagery

1. Introduction

The number and diversity of high-resolution settlement or buildings datasets has grown rapidly over the past decade, supported by developments in computing power, machine learning algorithms, and increasing spatiotemporal resolution of satellite imagery. Satellite imagery is typically processed through classification and/or segmentation (for raster datasets) or feature extraction (for vector building footprint datasets). Such datasets now have near-global coverage, no longer limiting data availability to countries with well-developed geospatial systems (Chamberlain et al., 2024). Current applications of settlement and building data are wide-ranging, including monitoring urban development (Domingo et al., 2023), identifying infrastructure at risk of hazards (Nirandjan et al., 2022), humanitarian response (Herfort et al., 2021), and modelling of population estimates (Leasure et al., 2020).

A key limitation of settlement and building footprint data has been the lack of attributes concerning building type, in particular attributes on residential and non-residential characteristics. This information has been included in some datasets, but these have been limited to individual counties (e.g. de Arruda et al., 2024). In 2023, the Global Human Settlement Layer was updated to include a built settlement product (GHS-BUILT-S) providing the first global dataset with residential/non-residential stratification. GHS-BUILT-S is derived from Sentinel-2 imagery using models trained on multi-country building footprint datasets with labelling from OpenStreetMap. GHS-BUILT-S has high utility, but the sparsity of other robust datasets on building characteristics, makes it difficult to assess accuracy, particularly for countries with limited geospatial data availability. To address this knowledge gap, we compare the GHS-BUILT-S dataset against comprehensive national datasets of residential household locations in Zambia and Germany, two countries with different built landscapes.

* h.chamberlain@soton.ac.uk

† gianluca.boo@soton.ac.uk

‡ a.j.tatem@soton.ac.uk

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Data

GHS-BUILT-S (R2023A; Pesaresi and Politis, 2023) consists of two rasters, one for all buildings and the other for non-residential buildings (NRES), with grid cell values representing the built-up surface area. The area of residential buildings is calculated by subtracting the NRES area from the total built-up area. We used the GHS-BUILT-S data for 2020; the version in WGS84 GCS (ESPG:4326) at 3 arc seconds resolution for Zambia, and the version projected to Mollweide PCS (ESPG:54009) at 100m resolution for Germany. These versions were chosen to ensure maximum spatiotemporal alignment with the reference datasets on residential households in each country.

The Zambia 2022 National Population and Housing Census collected geolocated data on all households, enabling the first national mapping of residential households in the country. This household data has recently been used as a binary mask of residential settlement to produce high-resolution population estimates (WorldPop and ZamStats, 2024) at 3 arc seconds spatial resolution. In Germany, the Federal Statistical Office conducts a register-based census, sampling 10% of the population nationally, most recently in 2022. We accessed gridded datasets on population and households at a spatial resolution of 100m (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2024).

2.2 Comparative Analysis

To enable comparison of datasets, we first reclassified GHS-BUILT-S into four classes: residential, non-residential, mixed use, and not built (Table 1). We also processed the household data from the Zambian and German 2022 censuses to provide binary rasters aligning with GHS-BUILT-S. An expanded definition of census residential locations, consisting of the binary raster with a 3x3 focal window incorporating the eight surrounding grid cells, was also defined. This expanded definition was included to account for potential small differences in locations of recorded households and built settlement. Unlike GHS-BUILT-S, the census datasets used in this analysis do not include non-residential buildings, therefore precluding stratification by non-residential and mixed-use classes. We compared the reclassified GHS-BUILT-S and census rasters by mapping and quantifying the combination of classes.

Table 1: Classification scheme applied to GHS-BUILT-S and census data

Class	Definition applied to GHS-BUILT-S	Definition applied to Census
Residential	Built area greater than 0 and non-residential built area equal to 0	One or more residential households (Zambia) or buildings (Germany).
Mixed	Non-residential built area and residential built area both greater than 0	Expanded definition includes eight surrounding grid cells (3x3 filter)
Non-residential	Non-residential built area greater than 0 and equal to the full built area	Count of residential households or buildings is 0. Not possible to distinguish between not built and non-residential
Not built	Built area equal to 0	

3. Results

Figure 1 compares the reclassified GHS-BUILT-S and census rasters, in terms of the count of grid cells per class. Germany and Zambia show similar patterns for residential settlement, with most grid cells that are classified as residential in the census also being classified as residential or mixed use in GHS-BUILT-S (Germany: 99.0%, Zambia: 90.4%). In Germany, the GHS data has a greater proportion of grid cells with non-residential buildings, likely reflecting differences in the built landscape between Germany and Zambia. Mapped examples comparing the datasets are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Count of grid cells in each class of the stratified datasets with GHS-BUILT-S on the upper axis and census on the lower axis. The spatial agreement between datasets is shown by flows between the upper and lower axes.

Across Zambia, 6,672,965 grid cells are identified as built settlement in GHS-BUILT-S, nearly all of which are residential (99.5%), with a very small number classified as mixed use (0.46%) or solely non-residential (<0.01%). In comparison, the Zambia household census raster has 1,525,866 grid cells classified as residential, with an additional 4,807,480 grid cells included when a 3x3 focal window is applied to include surrounding grid cells. Together, the binary and expanded definition of residential households cover 6,333,706 grid cells. There is, however, considerable spatial disagreement between these datasets. Of the 6,672,965 grid cells in Zambia classified as residential in GHS-BUILT-S, 1,366,743 (20.6%) are also classified as residential in the census raster, with a further 3,018,903 (45.5%) classified as residential within the 3x3 focal window. The remaining 34.0% of GHS-BUILT-S residential grid cells do not have residential buildings based on the census data.

For Germany, GHS-BUILT-S has 7,059,865 grid cells with built settlement, of which 80.1% are classified as residential, 19.8% mixed, and 0.06% non-residential. The census data for Germany has 2,550,364 grid cells with residential buildings, of which 80.3% correspond to GHS-BUILT-S residential and 18.8% to mixed. Nationally, there is a greater proportion of NRES grid cells in Germany (n=1,404,380), nearly all of which (99.7%) are classified as mixed use (Figure 2) due to a non-zero area of residential buildings in GHS-BUILT-S. Of the 1,400,489 grid cells in Germany classified as mixed use in GHS-BUILT-S, there is an approximately even split in terms of the mapped census classification: 34.3% classified as census residential, 30.3% expanded census residential and 35.5% with no census residential buildings. The number of GHS-BUILT-S grid cells classified as solely non-residential buildings is very low for both Germany (n=3,891) and Zambia (n=112).

Figure 2: Maps showing the built classification in GHS-BUILT-S and census data

4. Discussion

Our comparison of reclassified GHS-BUILT-S data against residential household census data shows similar patterns for Zambia and Germany. For both countries, the number of grid cells identified as residential in GHS-BUILT-S is greater than in the census-derived data, although this discrepancy is reduced for the 3x3 focal window of census residential locations. The accuracy of the GHS-BUILT-S non-residential component is harder to assess due to non-residential buildings not being included in either census dataset. For Germany, 19.9% of GHS-BUILT-S built grid cells were classified as non-residential or mixed use, whereas in Zambia only 0.5% of grid cells were classified as such. For both countries, the percentage of grid cells classified as having only non-residential buildings was less than 0.1%, which given the existence of contiguous areas with industrial and commercial buildings, seems unrealistically low. These results suggest that the area of non-residential buildings is underestimated in GHS-BUILT-S, both in terms of the number of grid cells and the total area of non-residential buildings in a grid cell.

With similar patterns observed across two countries with different built landscapes, we suggest that our findings are likely transferable, but this should be supported through further work. Geolocated household data collected in other countries as part of the 2020 census round may provide new opportunities for validating built settlement datasets, particularly in countries which have typically lacked such data previously. Given the wide range of application areas that stratified data on building types are relevant for, further work is needed to develop and robustly validate datasets.

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Biographies

Heather Chamberlain is a Senior Enterprise Fellow at the University of Southampton. Her work focusses on integrating geospatial data and quantitative methods for high-resolution mapping of populations, sociodemographics, and health. Most recently, this has been through the GRID3 project, collaborating with partners in Zambia and the Democratic Republic of Congo.

Gianluca Boo is a Senior Research Fellow at the University of Southampton building Bayesian modelling pipelines for high-resolution population mapping and estimation. His work focuses on developing bespoke Bayesian statistical models integrating demographic and geospatial data. He collaborates with national and international partners to improve decision-making in data-scarce countries.

Andrew J. Tatem is a Professor at the University of Southampton, specialising in mapping populations and their dynamics, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. His research interests include demographic and geospatial data for disease, disaster, and development applications, leading impactful global collaborations and pioneering methods for mapping vulnerable populations.